

Congenital corneal staphyloma

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Clinical Image

This is a 3-year-old girl , The right eye showed an opaque globular protrusion and the surface of the cornea was white neovascularized cornea The diameter of the cornea is larger than normal (Fig. 1). Ultrasound revealed a large eye, anteroposterior length 29 mm, with an abnormal anterior segment, no intraocular mass and normal flat retina and vitreous. Computed tomography (CT) showed an external pocket of the anterior aspect of the globe.

On clinical and supportive grounds, the diagnosis was congenital corneal staphyloma. The patient underwent enucleation of the right eye with placement of a prosthesis (Fig. 2). Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen revealed a congenital corneal staphyloma.

Figure 1: photograph of staphyloma appearance

Figure 2: photograph of surgical piece after enucleation